

ABOUT ABU ALI IBN SINA'S TRANSFORMATION OF A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE

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ABSTRACT

Ibn Sina showed that every living thing has a natural norm for its species. The creature with the most moderate clientele is the human being. His great achievement was that he was able to show his concept of the client in the example of the human body, from the general to the individual. Everyone has their own client.

The scientific heritage of Ibn Sina, who sealed his position in World medicine, is incredibly rich and is an invaluable treasure. Professor at the Catholic University of Louvain in Belgium today Yul Janssens "Ibn Sina and his influence on the arab and Latin World", "Abu Ali ibn Sino and his legacy"...Association Abu Ali ibn Sino-France president of professor Mark Bonnel, Dutch scientist Institute for the history of Science in Utrecht scientific activities of Professor Robert van Ghent ideas in the works of Ibn Sina there is another indication that benihath is valuable. Works by Ibn Sina deeper study is considered the most necessary factor in solving problems of today's era. The desire for us to know the history of our past gives us new-new facets of the past it is important that we are opening. Man and man, they influence, life and death, from living observed various issues, such as a goal, for several centuries people of creativity it is one of the mainstay that has attracted its attention.

Ecology is the science of the relationship between my body and the external environment Oikos - Greek household, habitat "logos" - science) the use of the expression Ernst Haeckel, a German natural scientist who lived in the nineteenth century (1834-1919) and is considered the father of the science of ecology. We must object to this, because, growing old a thousand years ago, our great compatriot, according to the scientist, the genius of medicine Abu Ali Ibn Sina, almost all environmental factors that are now called ecology, the influence of man, living beings on them, and, finally, this from popular expressions about the influence of factors on humans and living beings, KRL.

"Without dust, man would have lived for 1000 years", or: "if the air is balanced and clean, its(pneumatic) foreign if supplements are not added, It will be a guarantee of health, otherwise to various diseases causes " 1. As for the habitat environment, the Tib laws emphasize, it is said: "accommodation can affect the body in different ways: balan or low locality, soil composition and character, water abundance or rarity, the abundance of darkhts,

proximity to cemeteries or mines, etc. habitat it has significant significance when selected"" These thoughts are in the turmoil of the environment, and medical we will witness that it is relevant in Ecology. Therefore, later ecology debnom the given complex is named after Ibn Sina, at least "Medical it would be fair to be called the father of"Ecology".

Currently, environmental factors are divided into biotic and abiotic factors. But Ibn Dynamism of environmental factors in the causes of Health and illness of the Synod a thousand years ago his views on the person are shocking. Causes of alloma in ecological the fact that it gave a wide place to factors is due to its relevance today Ibn Sina Yanna is one-time verifier of the umribusiness of her teaching. We rightly believe that Ibn Sinani we can say that the founder of the doctrine of a healthy lifestyle. Ibn Sina fifricha, the only and reliable way to live a healthy life and have a long active life –this is a healthy lifestyle. And nutrition when shaping a healthy lifestyle culture, environmental education, exercise occupy an important place [6-15]. Alloma many people believe that health depends on whether the body has an excess or a small amount of blood it is believed that, in fact, it is not so much that health depends on the quality of blood correctly recognized. Health in modern terms-immanent of blood depends on the norm. In the work of Claude Bernard Ibn Sino, "mizoj" is a clear quality, a natural norm meaning.

"The way elements influence each other with their power as a result, a mood is formed that suits all of them. That's the mood it's Mizaj" Gap through quantities proportional to each other of four different quality elements it is not so difficult to realize that it is going about compatibility. Blood, bile, trade and lymphthe liquid is contained in a certain amount for each organism –"specific PCs"; this the four fluids are unique in measures of proportionality with each other in a certain amount. The norm of Health in this case is manifested in the form of a monotheism of four independent norms. Abu Mansur al-Qumri is also his mentor Ibn In affirming Sino's view on the subject, he says: "the exalted of the human body is in the case of this opposite four qualities will have stopped at a certain limit".

The teaching of Ibn Sina in the introduction of environmental education and upbringing in medicine it is advisable to take as a basis, to study it from the point of view of modernity. This for the purpose of landscaping, some of these non-native to the fauna of the country many plantings of ornamental trees are so much in the sense of disease ecogenesis in the conditions of our land, which is not useful, but high pollination, their one should not forget about the effect of a pathogen (including an allergen) on a person. Ibn Sina confessional as they did, to the landscape of the land reserved for residential purposes, their status, namely it is also necessary to approach the directions of urban planning as an environmental factor in the going [16-30].

The relationship of man between nature is studied by the science of Ecology. Current among the 15,000 subjects available in the day, the science of Ecology has its essence in depth, the presence of incredibly many networks and the importance of practical importance stand out.

Central Asian population with one of the largest states in Jati the emergence of environmental problems in Uzbekistan, its natural environment, people Health, which is being monitored. Anashu environmental problemsin order by giving environmental knowledge to the entire population of Uzbekistan, especially young people, they have shaping ecological culture is a pressing issue today.

In conclusion, Ibn Sina argues that with human health, nature and its ecological it was in time that he realized the dialectical connection between his factors. In fact a healthy person is a product of a healthy nature, in the norm of life indicators of the biosphere more than 7 billion inhabitants on Planet Earth can live peacefully only if they have survived. The way that only the perfect humanity, realizing the norms of the existence of nature, corrupts them in life does not.

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